

FRACTURE AND FATIGUE CHARACTERISATION OF THE SHOT-EARTH 772

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Among the earthen construction techniques, the innovative shot-earth technique employs a material, named shot-earth, which is a dry mixture composed of excavated soil, aggregates and water, where the soil may be either unstabilised or stabilised by a chemical binder. More precisely, the mixture here examined is the shot-earth 772, consisting of 7 parts of soil, 7 parts of aggregates, 2 parts of cement (by volume) and about 3% of water (by volume). The fracture toughness of such a material is herein evaluated by applying a method recently proposed by the authors, named the Modified Two-Parameter Model. Then, both compressive and flexural fatigue tests are performed under different levels of maximum stress, being the fatigue ratio equal to zero, and the corresponding S-N curves are determined. Finally, the above experimental campaigns are numerically simulated by employing a micromechanical model, implemented in a non-linear 2D finite element homemade code.

Keywords: Fracture toughness, Micromechanical numerical model, Modified Two-Parameter Model, S-N curves

INTRODUCTION

The first use of earth building techniques dates from the Neolithic period (about 10000 BC) in the Mesopotamia region and, accordingly, such techniques can be considered among the oldest construction techniques known to mankind (Vantadori et al. [1]). Among them, it is worth mentioning: cut blocks, poured earth, super adobe, adobe, cob, rammed earth, compressed stabilised earth blocks, wattle and daub, and shaped earth. Some of these techniques employ stabilised soil, being cement the most common stabiliser. The stabilisation increases both cohesion and strength of soil, and enhances the soil resistance against water induced erosion, that is, the durability (Vantadori et al. [2]).

Nowadays, these techniques are still widely employed in less developed countries, where almost 50% of population lives in earthen constructions. Nevertheless, also in developed countries the traditional earth building techniques, which exploit natural and locally available materials, are increasingly attracting the interest of many researchers as well as building companies. As a matter of fact, earth buildings represent a possible eco-friendly alternative for the construction industry, which is responsible for about 30% of carbon dioxide emissions and consumes more raw materials than any other sector (Pacheco-Torgal and Jalali [3]).

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In this particular context, earth building techniques guarantee low carbon dioxide emissions and very low pollution impacts. As a matter of fact, earth is cheap, locally available in large quantities, and can be obtained directly from the excavation of foundations, avoiding any transportation. Low energy is also required for these building techniques and, after demolition, raw earth is completely recyclable and reusable. Moreover, earthen construction materials are characterized by both low thermal conductivity and high hygroscopic properties (Anglade et al. [4]).

An innovative technique, among the earthen construction ones, is that named shot-earth technique, which employs a material, named shot-earth, consisting of excavated soil, aggregates, water, and eventually cement as stabilizer (Colpo et al. [5]). The applications of the shot-earth are those typical of dry shotcrete, mainly consisting in new structures, repairs and rehabilitations, and slope and surface protection (Kalhori et al. [6] and Leblouba et al. [7]). In the context of new structures, shot-earth can be easily employed for the realization of walls, slabs, columns, shells, domes and other structural elements, especially when complex geometric configurations are required. Moreover, shot-earth can be conveniently employed when the traditional concrete casting is characterised by operational difficulties, such as in the case of overhead structures, walls behind pipe, and in presence of other mechanical obstacles.

The present paper is dedicated to the fracture and fatigue characterization of a specific shot-earth, that is, the shot-earth 772, which is made of: seven parts of soil, seven parts of aggregates, two parts of cement, and about 3% of water by volume. Such a proportion between soil, aggregates and cement gives the hardened material mechanical properties similar to those of a low-strength concrete suitable for structural applications (Vantadori et al. [2]). Both fracture and fatigue characterisation of the shot-earth 772 are needed to widen the range of its use in the construction field. Therefore, the fracture toughness is herein evaluated by applying a method recently proposed by the present authors, named the Modified Two-Parameter Model (Carpinteri et al. [8], Vantadori et al. [9]). Then, both compressive and flexural fatigue tests are performed under different levels of maximum stress, being the fatigue ratio equal to zero, and the corresponding S-N curves are determined. Finally, the above experimental campaigns are numerically simulated by employing a micromechanical model, implemented in a non-linear 2D finite element homemade code (Scorza [10], Brighenti et al. [11]).

CONSTITUENTS AND MIXTURE OF THE SHOT-EARTH 772

The shot-earth 772 (named for simplicity “shot-earth” in the following) considered in the present work was a mixture composed by seven parts of soil stabilised with two parts of cement, seven parts of aggregates, and about 3% of water by volume. Note that the water was directly added at the spraying nozzle when the stream is projected at a high velocity onto a receiving surface. Details may be found in the work of Vantadori et al. [2].

The soil was an excavated soil (extracted after the removal of a top-soil layer) characterised by a large content of organic matter. After the excavation, the soil was stockpiled and left to dry for a few days (depending on both season and soil type) without controlling temperature and relative humidity. Then, the soil was sieved in order to remove any stones, and milled. The as-received soil employed here was classified as a poorly graded sand with silt, according to the Unified Soil Classification System implemented in the ASTM D2487-17 standard [12], whereas the washed soil was classified as a silty sand, according to the same standard.

The cement for the soil stabilisation was a CEM I 42.5 N Portland cement, complying with the EN 197-1 standard [13].

The aggregate was a commercial aggregate for concrete, made of carbonate sedimentary rocks (mainly limestone), complying with the EN 12620 standard [14]. The maximum aggregate size was 8 mm.

The microstructural analysis and the chemical analysis of both the mix constituents and the shot-earth may be found in the work of Vantadori et al. [2].

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF THE SHOT-EARTH 772

The mechanical properties of the shot-earth were determined by carrying out both flexural and compression tests [1].

The flexural tests were performed under three-point bending on three prismatic specimens, according to the EN 12390-5 standard [15].

The tested specimens were characterised by nominal sizes equal to 100mm(width)x100mm(depth)x375mm(length) and a nominal span equal to 300 mm. The tests were carried out by using a universal testing machine Instron 8502 Plus, with a load cell up to 25 kN and accuracy of 0.5%. The tests were performed under load control with rate equal to 130 N/s up to failure, being the loading direction normal to the spraying one.

The average value of the flexural strength f_{cf} was found to be equal to 3.51 MPa, with a standard deviation of ± 0.89 MPa.

The compression tests were performed on eight cubic specimens, according to the EN 12390-3 standard [16].

The tested specimens were characterised by nominal sizes equal to 100mmx100mmx100mm. The tests were carried out by using a standard compression testing machine, with load cell up to 300 kN and accuracy of 1%. The tests were performed under load control with rate equal to 0.5 MPa/s up to failure, being the loading direction normal to the spraying one.

The average value of the compressive strength f_c was equal to 14.57 MPa, with a standard deviation of ± 2.55 MPa.

FRACTURE BEHAVIOUR OF THE SHOT-EARTH 772

Fracture toughness tests were performed on six notched prismatic specimens under three-point bending, according to both the 50-FMC [17] and 89-FMT RILEM [18] recommendations and the Modified Two-Parameter Model (MTPM) [8,9], in order to determine the elastic modulus and the fracture toughness of the shot-earth being considered.

The tested specimens were characterised by nominal sizes equal to 80mm(depth)x40mm(width)x375mm(length). A notch was performed in the lower part of the middle-cross section, with a nominal length equal to 26.7 mm (notch width lower than 1.45 mm), whereas the nominal span was equal to 320 mm.

The tests were carried out by using a universal testing machine Instron 8862, with a load cell up to 100 kN and an accuracy of 0.1%. The tests were performed under Crack Mouth Opening Displacement (CMOD) control with an average rate of the clip gauge equal to 0.2 mm/h, being the loading direction normal to the spraying one.

FIGURE 1 Load against crack mouth opening displacement curves obtained from the fracture toughness tests.

The load against CMOD curves are shown in Figure 1. It is worth noticing that no acceptable failures according to the RILEM recommendations were registered for two specimens and, accordingly, only four curves are displayed in Figure 1.

It can be observed that such curves are quite similar to each other, both in the inner elastic branch, at the peak load and in the softening branch, that is, rather homogeneous results were obtained.

The elastic modulus, E , and the fracture toughness, $K_{(I+II)C}^S$, were computed according to the MTPM [8,9]. In particular, the average value of the elastic modulus was equal to 9450.56 MPa, with a standard deviation of ± 1227.39 MPa, whereas the average value of the fracture toughness was equal to $0.33 \text{ MPa(m)}^{0.5}$, with a standard deviation of $\pm 0.05 \text{ MPa(m)}^{0.5}$.

Furthermore, it was observed that cracks, starting from the notch tip, usually deflected due to the inhomogeneities embedded in the shot-earth 772. An average values of kinking crack angle was found equal to 23° (interested readers may find more details related to the experimental crack paths in [1]). It can be stated that most of the above cracks grew under Mixed Mode even if a remote pure Mode I loading was applied to the specimens.

FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR OF THE SHOT-EARTH 772

Both fatigue flexural tests and fatigue compression tests were performed.

Ten fatigue flexural tests were performed under three-point bending cyclic loading on prismatic specimens, characterised by nominal sizes equal to 100mm(width)x100mm(depth)x375mm(length). The nominal span was equal to 300 mm. The tests were carried out by using a universal testing machine Instron 8502 Plus, with a load cell up to 25 kN and an accuracy of 0.5%. The tests were performed under load control up to failure, by applying a sinusoidal signal for the stress (frequency of 5 Hz and fatigue ratio equal to zero), being the loading direction normal to the spraying one. The maximum value of the applied stress, σ_{max} , normalised with respect to the average value of the flexural strength ($f_{cf}=3.51$ MPa), was made to vary from 0.53 to 0.82.

Twelve fatigue compression tests were performed on cubic specimens, characterised by nominal sizes 100mmx100mmx100mm. The tests were carried out by using an in-house designed dynamic testing machine equipped with a 500 kN actuator and a load cell up to 1000 kN and accuracy of 1%. The tests were performed under load control up to failure, by applying a sinusoidal signal for the stress (frequency of 5 Hz and fatigue ratio equal to zero), being the loading direction normal to the spraying one. The maximum value of the applied stress, σ_{max} , normalised with respect to the average value of the compressive strength ($f_c=14.57$ MPa), was made to vary from 0.45 to 0.75.

It is worth noticing that, when fatigue failure did not occur within $2(10)^6$ loading cycles, the test result was referred to a run-out.

The Wöhler curves for both cyclic bending and cyclic compression were determined by interpolating the fatigue results with a power function, and are plotted in Figure 2. The equations of such curves are given by:

$$\sigma_a = 1.845N_{f,exp}^{-0.03724} \tag{1}$$

$$\sigma_a = 6.959N_{f,exp}^{-0.04318} \tag{2}$$

being $N_{f,exp}$ the experimental number of loading cycles to failure.

FIGURE 2 Wöhler curves for cyclic bending (symbols in red) and cyclic compression (symbols in blue), determined by interpolating the fatigue results with a power function. The symbols with arrow represent the run-outs.

NUMERICAL MODELING OF THE SHOT-EARTH 772

A micromechanical numerical model, proposed in the past by some of the present authors [10,11], is here employed to simulate the fracture toughness tests and the fatigue tests (both fatigue flexural tests and fatigue compression tests) described in the previous Sections. This model is implemented in a non-linear 2D FE home-made code in standard Fortran language, where the matrix is assumed to have a brittle behaviour, whereas the discontinuities due to the fracture process are modelled

through a suitable modification of the material properties by means of a cohesive law. Further details can be found in the work by Scorza et al. [19].

Firstly, the fracture behaviour of the shot-earth 772 was modelled in order to validate the input data; then, such data were used into the model to simulate the material fatigue behaviour.

Input data validation

For fracture simulation, the notched prismatic specimens subjected to the fracture toughness tests were modelled by considering the mean geometrical sizes measured during the experimental campaign, that is: 83.7mm(depth)x48.1mm(width)x375.0mm(length). A notch in the lower part of the middle-cross section was considered, with a length equal to 27.2 mm (notch width equal to 1.45 mm), whereas the nominal span was equal to 320 mm.

The input data (related to the material properties) for the above model were taken from the abovementioned experimental results, except for the Poisson coefficient and the energy release rate, which were taken from Vantadori et al. [1] and were assumed to be equal to 0.2 and 25 N/m, respectively.

A mesh discretisation of 720 four-node quadrilateral plate elements was set after convergence analysis performed on the computed stress field. A progressive vertical displacement at the top point of the central cross-section was imposed in the model, recording both the corresponding reaction force and the CMOD.

The numerical load vs CMOD curve is compared in Figure 3 with the experimental scatter band. A satisfactory agreement between numerical and experimental results can be observed, since the numerical curve is mostly inside the experimental scatter band, both in the inner elastic branch, at the peak load and in the softening branch.

The peak load is underestimated by 12.3% from the numerical model, being the obtained numerical value equal to 0.64 kN, although it is inside the experimental data range (0.73 ± 0.09 kN).

FIGURE 3 Numerical load against crack mouth opening displacement curve obtained by the present micromechanical model, compared with the corresponding experimental scatter band related to the fracture toughness tests.

Moreover, the numerical fracture toughness was evaluated by applying the MTPM to the numerical load against CMOD curve, by using the unloading compliance computed in correspondence of the peak load, and by assuming a pure Mode I crack propagation, that is, the kinking crack angle was equal to 0° . The fracture toughness was computed equal to $0.42 \text{ MPa(m)}^{0.5}$, that is, greater than the experimental one, even if very close to the experimental data range.

Simulation of fatigue tests

For fatigue simulation, the prismatic specimens and the cubic ones, subjected to the fatigue flexural tests and fatigue compression tests, respectively, were modelled by considering the mean geometrical sizes measured during the experimental campaign, that is: $101.6\text{mm}(\text{width}) \times 101.4\text{mm}(\text{depth}) \times 375\text{mm}(\text{length})$ for the prismatic specimen subjected to cyclic bending, and $100.4\text{mm}(\text{width}) \times 100.5\text{mm}(\text{depth}) \times 100.7\text{mm}(\text{height})$ for the cubic specimen subjected to cyclic compression.

Other input data were the following material properties. More precisely, the mechanical properties were the same as those assumed for the fracture toughness model presented in the previous Section. In addition, as far as the fatigue properties are concerned, the S-N curves obtained from both cyclic bending and compression tests (described by Eqs (1) and (2), respectively) were used as input data.

Moreover, both the loading and the boundary conditions were defined in order to properly simulate the experimental ones.

Related to the loading conditions, the maximum number of blocks of loading cycles (together with the corresponding number of cycles) and the number of load steps were set.

For each block of loading cycles, the load was applied by steps and, for each step, the stress and strain fields were computed according to the material constitutive law. The convergence conditions on the nodal displacements and the unbalanced forces were checked: if such conditions were satisfied, next load increment followed, otherwise another iteration started. These iterations were repeated until the final load step was reached.

Then, at the end of each block of loading cycles, the damage parameter, d , was computed in each finite element of the model.

The procedure iterated until either the maximum number of blocks of loading cycles or a critical value, d_c , of the damage parameter was reached, whichever occurred first.

In the present simulations, the maximum number of blocks of loading cycles and the number of load steps were equal to 20 and 3, respectively. Moreover, the damage parameter d was computed by exploiting the well-known Miner linear rule for fatigue damage accumulation (Miner [20]):

$$d = \sum_{k=1}^p \frac{n_k}{N_k} \quad (3)$$

where p is the total number of blocks of loading cycles, and k is the current block. Moreover, n_k is the number of loading cycles of the k -th block, and N_k is the number of loading cycles to failure for load level and stress ratio characterising the k -th block, computed according to the material S-N curve.

The damage parameter was used in the model to update the mechanical properties of the material, such as the elastic modulus, accounting for the damaging effect of cyclic loading, according to the following simplified relationship:

$$E_f = E(1 - d) \tag{4}$$

where E_f is the reduced elastic modulus. If $d = 0$, no degradation of the material mechanical properties occurred (i.e. $E_f = E$), whereas the critical condition was reached when the damage parameter was equal to 1 (i.e. $d = dc=1$ and $E_f \rightarrow 0$) and a condition of incipient failure was assumed. Note that both d and E_f were computed in each FE of the model.

The mesh discretisations, obtained after a convergence analysis related to the stress field, were characterised by 696 four-node quadrilateral plate elements for the fatigue flexural model, and by 240 four-node quadrilateral plate elements for the fatigue compression model.

TABLE 1 Numerical fatigue lifetimes, N_f , obtained through the fatigue flexural model and corresponding experimental ones, $N_{f,exp}$, for each normalised loading level, σ_{max}/f_{cf} .

Specimen No.	σ_{max}/f_{cf} (-)	$N_{f,exp}$ (cycles)	N_f (cycles)	$N_{f,exp}/N_f$ (-)
F1	0.67	1234493	1500000	0.82
F2	0.73	1087360	340000	3.20
F3	0.73	251460	340000	0.74
F4	0.75	83800	48000	1.75
F5	0.78	43100	18000	2.39
F6	0.82	23715	4400	5.39

TABLE 2 Numerical fatigue lifetimes, N_f , obtained through the fatigue compression model and corresponding experimental ones, $N_{f,exp}$, for each normalised loading level, σ_{max}/f_c .

Specimen No.	σ_{max}/f_c (-)	$N_{f,exp}$ (cycles)	N_f (cycles)	$N_{f,exp}/N_f$ (-)
C1	0.55	1570900	2000000	0.79
C2	0.55	1865317	2000000	0.93
C3	0.60	831414	420000	1.98
C4	0.60	855405	420000	2.04
C5	0.65	122394	65000	1.88
C6	0.65	196307	65000	3.00
C7	0.70	25065	11000	2.28
C8	0.70	14678	11000	1.33
C9	0.75	2439	2100	1.16
C10	0.75	1826	2100	0.87

As far as the fatigue flexural model is concerned, the results obtained in terms of numerical fatigue lifetimes, N_f , are listed in Table 1 and compared with the experimental ones, $N_{f,exp}$, by considering only the failed specimens. The normalised loading levels, σ_{max}/f_{cf} , are also reported in Table 1.

It can be observed that 50% of results fall into the scatter band 2, whereas 67% into the scatter band 3. However, at least conservative estimations were obtained for the two points falling out the scatter band 3.

The damage was found to be located at the bottom of the middle cross-section, in accordance with the experiments, where the stress reaches its maximum value. In particular, the maximum damage values attained after 1100, 2200 and 3300 loading cycles were equal to 0.26, 0.52 and 0.78, respectively.

As far as the fatigue compression model is concerned, the results obtained in terms of numerical fatigue lifetimes N_f are listed in Table 2 and compared with the experimental ones $N_{f,exp}$, by considering only the failed specimens. The normalised loading levels σ_{max}/f_c are also reported in Table 2.

It can be observed that 60% of results fall into the scatter band 2, whereas 100% into the scatter band 3.

The damage was found to be located quite distributed in the central part of the model. In particular, the maximum damage values attained after 500, 1000 and 1500 loading cycles were equal to 0.22, 0.49 and 0.74, respectively.

CONCLUSIONS

The present research work has been devoted to the fracture and fatigue characterization of a specific mixture of shot-earth, named shot-earth 772, consisting of 7 parts of soil, 7 parts of aggregates, 2 parts of cement (by volume) and about 3% of water (by volume).

More precisely, three-point bending fracture tests have been carried out to analyse the fracture behaviour and to determine the elastic modulus as well as the fracture toughness according to the Modified Two-Parameter Model.

Moreover, both compressive and flexural fatigue tests have been carried out to analyse the fatigue behaviour under flexural and compressive loading, and the corresponding S-N curves have been determined.

Finally, a 2D home-made FE numerical model has been used to simulate the fatigue tests, after the input data validation carried out by simulating the above fracture tests. In particular, the numerical fatigue lifetimes have been compared with the corresponding experimental ones, highlighting that:

- for pulsating bending, 50% of the results fall into the scatter band 2, whereas 67% into the scatter band 3, with conservative estimations for the two points falling out the scatter band 3;
- for pulsating compression, 60% of results fall into the scatter band 2, whereas 100% into the scatter band 3.

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